

The Impact of Visual Aids in Enhancing Presentation Skills

Ng Xin Li, Chong Yu Qian, Dr. Logenthini A/P Mariappan

^{1,2,3} Raffles University, Malaysia

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Abstract: This paper focuses on experimentally investigating visual aids in enhancing presentation skills. This paper aims to inform readers about visual aids and how they can utilize them to enhance their presentational abilities. We undertook experiments to support the hypothesis of visual aids can enhance our presentation skills. A total of 100 people cooperated with this study, including 34 females and 66 males. Thus, new and efficient approaches are needed to improve our presentation skills by using visual aids. The result obtained in this research includes how to optimize the present, the audience's opinion of the speaker(questionnaire), etc. We carried out several studies which have demonstrated that visual aids can greatly increase our presentational capabilities.

Keywords: investigating visual aids, enhancing presentation skills.

1. INTRODUCTION

Visual aids include personal appearance, objects and props, demonstrations, posters and flip charts, audio and video, handouts, and slideware (LibreTexts Social Sciences, 2022). Moreover, according to the Cambridge dictionary, visual aids are something that you are shown, such as a picture, film, or map, to help you understand or remember information (Cambridge Dictionary, n.d.).

But it can be said visual aids play a major role in the presentation. Visual aids play a vital role, especially during this online mode, it is preferable to use visual aids that could enhance the readers' attention. In addition to keeping your audience engaged, they can help you to make your point. The saying "a picture tells a thousand words" has a good reason and reminds us of what we want to say (Skills You Need, n.d.).

It is well known that the Covid-19 pandemic has pushed us to use online mode for every aspect of our lives, including business and education. Throughout this period, Visual aids were so useful to all of us because they helped us to improve and enhance our presentations. As part of this study, we are going to discuss the impact that visual aids have on presentations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Presentation skills

Graduates with outstanding communication abilities are in high demand among employers. As a result, a student's performance in class becomes crucial to providing effective learning opportunities. Most students and teachers believed that developing presentation skills or teaching them how to address a number of individuals were crucial presentation goals (ACM Digital Library, n.d.).

There are a lot of skills in presenting and the three most important ones are practice, staying relaxed, and slowing down (Alvernia University, 2015).

First of all, we must be fully prepared before the speech. As the saying goes: “practice makes perfect”. We have to prepare a complete PowerPoint and speech before giving a speech, and we have to prepare for the accident in advance so that we will not be in a mess. Not only that, but we also need to stay relaxed and enjoy when giving a speech. This not only makes the audience feel comfortable but also reduces the presenter’s nervousness. Finally, we should never speak faster even if we feel nervous during the speech. First, the audience may not hear the information you express clearly. Second, the speech time will become very short if you speed up the speech, which will affect the score.

Impact of Visual aids in presentation skills

Almost all presentations can benefit from the appropriate use of visual aids. These can include handouts, overhead projections, whiteboard sketches, PowerPoint slides, and a variety of certain other props. One significant nonverbal component of your communication that you influence is visual aids. The impact of visual aids in the presentation includes making your speech become more interesting, conveying difficult or fascinating information in a brief amount of time, assisting the audience in utilizing and remembering the knowledge, and so on (University Of Minnesota Libraries, n.d.)

When we are using visual aids in presentation it will make our otherwise dull topic interesting and a presentation that is too monotonous will only make the audience feel sleepy. A good ppt will also let the audience know the main content of the class in a short time. On the other hand, a PowerPoint that is too long will make the audience feel bored because they don't know what to focus on. Nay, the use of visual aids will also enhance the audience's memory points. For example, raise your voice when you get to important points or show a video about a subject in class.

Benefits of visual aids

By using visual aids during a speech, the effectiveness of the speech can be greatly enhanced. It is helpful in many speeches to present objects, images, quotes, or data clearly and dramatically so that it can be understood by the listeners. Even though visual aids come in different types and are used for different purposes, there are quite a few benefits and tips to remember when dealing with any kind of additional evidence that is presented to an audience when it comes to visual aids (University of Pittsburgh, n.d.).

It is also very important that you use visual aids in your presentation so that you can maintain the attention of your audience (Miller, 2015). Up to 65% of people learn best visually, and this can be attributed to the fact that there is a significant portion of the brain dedicated to visual function. When a relevant visual is added to an oral presentation, it helps to keep the audience’s eyes focused forward and increases their retention of the information that is being presented. It has been shown that when oral and visual learning is combined, the rate of retention is greatly increased (Miller, 2015).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study used a quantitative research design. 5 Likert scale survey questionnaire was used and the samples were chosen randomly. Total Of 100 sample participants responded to the questionnaire and the response was recorded. The total score with the percentage was presented in the findings of the study.

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS

Part 1: Demographic

Table 1: Age

Age	17-22		23-28		29-34		35 and above	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
	85	85%	6	6%	5	5%	4	4%

According to the data survey, the age group that filled out the most forms was 17 to 22 years old, which accounted for 85%.

Table 2: Gender

Gender	Male		Female	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
	66	66%	34	34%

Table 3: Mother tongue

Mother tongue	Chines		English		Malay		Tamil and other	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
	83	83%	5	5%	7	7%	5	5%

According to the data, native Chinese speakers accounted for 83% of the data. English and Tamil/other accounted for 5% each. Malay accounts for 7%.

Table 4: Area

Area	Rural		Urban	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
	76	76%	24	24%

Most are from rural areas, accounting for 76 percent, the data showed.

Table 5: Education level

Education level	Primary		Secondary		University	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
	0	0%	68	68%	32	32%

Statistics show that most people choose to work in society after finishing middle school.

Table 6: Language used for Presentation

The language used for the Presentation	English		Chinese		Malay and other	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
	63	63%	29	29%	8	8%

Statistics show that most people can use English as the language of speech while the minority choose to use Bahasa Malaysia or other languages.

Table 7: Creativity toward presentation

Creativity toward presentation	Less creative		Creative		More creative	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
	29	29%	60	60%	11	11%

The data shows that most people are in the middle of the pack when it comes to creativity.

Table 8: Do you consider yourself a good presenter

Do you consider yourself a good presenter?	Yes		No	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
	33	33%	67	67%

Statistics show that 67 people don't think they're good presenters. Maybe it's modesty or maybe it's just the truth.

Table 9: How often do you use visual aids

How often do you use visual aids	At least once a week		A few times per month		Less frequently than that		Never	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
	19	19%	47	47%	20	20%	14	14%

According to the data, people use visual aids less than once a month. But it's not like it's never been used.

Table 10: When do you start using visual aids

When do you start using visual aids	Primary		Secondary		University		Work	
	N	%	N	%	N	%	N	%
	14	14%	58	58%	19	19%	9	9%

Statistics show that most people are already exposed to visual aids in middle school. Only 9% were exposed to visual aids after work.

Part2: Question

Figure 1: Taking a class to improve the presentation skills

In the first question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they have been taking classes to improve their presentation skills, almost 10 respondents which are about 10% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 57 respondents agreed that I have been taking classes to improve my presentation skills. 16 respondents disagreed and 3 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly, 14 respondents which are about 14% responded that they were the neutral response. It can be seen that most people choose to learn to improve their presentation skills

Figure 2: When the presentation has many memorable memories

In the second question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they have many memorable memories about the presentation, almost 13 respondents which is about 13% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 58 respondents agreed that I have many memorable memories of the presentation. 15 respondents that they disagreed and no respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly,14 respondents which are about 14% responded that they were the neutral response. Most people have deep memories from their presentations. It could be the nervousness of giving a first speech or the funny moment of giving a speech.

Figure 3: Get more responses from the audiences

In the third question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they hope they can get more responses from audiences, almost 23 respondents which are about 23.2% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 54 respondents agreed that they hope they can get more responses from audiences. 11 respondents that they disagreed and no respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly,11 respondents which are about 11.1% responded that they were the neutral response. Statistics show that most people want a response from the audience when they give a speech. In my opinion, I think the response of the audience can reduce the tension of the presenters.

Figure 4: Takes a lot of courage when the presentation

In the fourth question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they had to muster up a lot of courage before the presentation, almost 22 respondents which are about 22% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 54 respondents agreed that they had to muster up a lot of courage before the presentation. 14 respondents that they disagreed and 2 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly,8 respondents which are about 8% responded that they were the neutral response. The data show that only a few people don't need a lot of courage before giving a speech. I think getting up the courage before I give a presentation makes me feel confident and give a better presentation.

Figure 5: Do present at least 10 times in the life

In the fifth question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they have been presenting at least 10 times in their life, almost 28 respondents which are about 28% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 36 respondents agreed that they have been presenting at least 10 times in their life. 28 respondents that they disagreed and 5 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly,3 respondents which are about 3% responded that they were the neutral response. This statistic shows that most people present more than 10 times in their life. Because we need to give presentations to leaders not only during class but also during work

Figure 6: Before the presentation, start have a fully prepared

In the six questions for the perception part where the respondents were asked if they were fully prepared before their presentation started, almost 12 respondents which are about 12% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 63 respondents agreed that they were fully prepared before their presentation started. 19 respondents that they disagreed and no respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly, 6 respondents which are about 6% responded that they were the neutral response. My thinking is the same as the data. I think giving a present fully prepared greatly reduces the chance of making mistakes.

Figure 7: Enjoy the presentation

In the seven questions for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they enjoy it when they make presentations, almost 13 respondents which are about 13.1% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 42 respondents agreed that they enjoy it when they make presentations. 25 respondents that they disagreed and 9 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly, 10 respondents which are about 10.1% responded that they were neutral response. Most people enjoy the moment of giving a speech. I feel that I enjoy the time of presentation.

Figure 8: When using visual aids have faced many problems

In the eighth question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they have been facing many problems in using visual aids, almost 13 respondents which are about 13.1% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 42 respondents agreed that they have been facing many problems in using visual aids. 25 respondents that they disagreed and 9 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly,10 respondents are about10.1% responded that they neutral response. Take me for example, I was also been facing many problems in using visual aids.

Figure 9: Visual aids are important during presentations

In the nine-question perception part where the respondents were asked on they think visual aids are important during the presentation, almost 9 respondents which are about 9% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 46 respondents agreed that they think visual aids are important during presentations. 28 respondents that they disagreed and no respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly,17 respondents which are about 17% responded that they neutral response.

Figure 10: Use a variety of visual aids when the presentation

In the ten questions for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they usually use many types of visual aids when they were present, almost 12 respondents which are about 12% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 49 respondents agreed that they usually use many types of visual aids when they were present. 22 respondents that they disagreed and 3 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly, 14 respondents which are about 14% responded that they were the neutral response. Follow the data shows that they usually use many types of visual aids when they are present.

Figure 11: Didn't face any issues while the presentation

In the eleven questions for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they don't have to face any problems when presenting, almost 6 respondents which are about 6% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 23 respondents agreed that they don't have to face any problems when presenting. 48 respondents that they disagreed and 19 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly, 4 respondents which are about 4% responded that they were neutral response. Most people have been facing many problems when presenting.

Figure 12: use more visual aids when present

In the twelve questions for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they hope the presenter will use more visual aids when presenting, almost 19 respondents which are about 19.4% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 65 respondents agreed that they hope the presenter will use more visual aids when presenting. 4 respondents that they disagreed and 11 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly,11 respondents which is about 11.2% responded that a neutral response. The use of visual aids can make the presentation more vivid and interesting and attract the audience's attention.

Figure 13:

In the thirteenth question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they know all the types of visual aids, almost 3 respondents which are about 3% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 29 respondents agreed that they know all the types of visual aids. 44 respondents that they disagreed and 9 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly,14 respondents about 14.1% responded that they were the neutral response. Most people just use a little part of visual aids such as ppt, body language, etc. Others that are rarely used are not known.

Figure 14:

In the fourteenth question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they can master and use visual aids smoothly, almost 1 respondent which is about 1% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 33 respondents agreed that they can master and use visual aids smoothly. 46 respondents that they disagreed and 9 respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly, 11 respondents which are about 11% responded that they were neutral responses. This shows that most people are not very good at mastering visual aids.

Figure 15: Presenter

In the last question for the perception part where the respondents were asked on they think should about the presenter having much eye contact with the audience when presenting, almost 37 respondents which are about 37% responded Strongly agreed. Almost 54 respondents agreed that the presenter should have many eyes contact with the audience when presenting. 4 respondents that they disagreed and no respondents strongly disagreed with this content. Lastly, 5 respondents which are about 5% responded that they were neutral response. I think eye contact can bring the speaker closer to the audience. It also makes the audience more focused on listening.

5. CONCLUSION

The study has found that visual aids exactly enhancing our presentation skills. The study contributes to our understanding of how to strengthen our presentation skills by using visual aids. A quantitative research design was used for this investigation. The survey used a 5-point Likert scale, and the samples were selected at random. 100 sample participant in total answered the questionnaire, and the answers were logged. These data suggest that presentation skills can be achieved through using visual aids smoothly. Students should be exposed to visual aids as early as possible to improve their presentation skills.

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